

Fixed Point Theorems for Some Iteration Processes with Generalized Zamfirescu Mappings in Uniformly Convex Banach Spaces

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Abstract

The paper establish fixed point theorems for some iteration processes in uniformly convex Banach spaces with generalized Zamfirescu mappings. Our results improve a multitude of recent results in literature. .

Keywords: Generalised Zamfirescu Mappings, Fixed Point, Uniformly Convex Banach Spaces, Iterative Scheme.

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1 Introduction

Let (Q, d) be a complete metric space, $T : Q \rightarrow Q$ be a selfmap of Q . The set $F_T = \{x \in Q : Tx = x\}$ is the set of fixed point of T in X . Let Q be a non-empty closed and convex subset of a Banach space X .

A Banach space is a complete normed linear space. A Banach space $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ is said to be uniformly convex, if for every $\epsilon > 0$, there exists a $\delta > 0$ such that for all $x, y \in X$ with $\|x\| \leq 1$, $\|y\| \leq 1$ and $\|x - y\| \geq \epsilon$ then $\|\frac{1}{2}(x + y)\| \leq 1 - \delta$.

The following result is due to Zamfirescu [1] in 1972.

Theorem 1.1. [1] Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and $T : X \rightarrow X$ be a mapping for

which there exist real numbers α , β and γ satisfying $0 \leq \alpha < 1$, $0 \leq \beta < 0.5$ and $0 \leq \gamma < 0.5$ such that for each $x, y \in X$ at least one of the following is true:

$$(Z_1) \quad d(Tx, Ty) \leq \alpha d(x, y),$$

$$(Z_2) \quad d(Tx, Ty) \leq \beta[d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty)],$$

$$(Z_3) \quad d(Tx, Ty) \leq \gamma[d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)].$$

Let

$$\delta = \max\left\{\alpha, \frac{\beta}{1-\beta}, \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma}\right\}.$$

where δ satisfy $0 \leq \delta < 1$.

A mapping T satisfying the contractive conditions (Z_1) , (Z_2) and (Z_3) in Theorem 1.1 above is called Zamfirescu operator.

Remark 1: For the proof of Theorem 1.1 (see [2]). Also shown below:

If Z_1 holds then we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_2, x_1) &= d(Tx_1, Tx_0) \\ &\leq \alpha d(x_1, x_0) \\ d(x_3, x_2) &= d(Tx_2, Tx_1) \\ &\leq \alpha^2 d(x_1, x_0) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_{n+1}, x_n) &\leq \alpha^n d(x_1, x_0), \quad \forall = 1, 2, 3, \dots \\ d(x_{n+p}, x_n) &= d(x_n, x_{n+p}), \\ &= \sum_{k=n}^{n+p-1} d(x_{k+1}, x_k). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_{n+1}, x_n) &= d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \\ &\leq \alpha d(x_n, x_{n-1}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_{n+2}, x_{n+1}) &= d(Tx_{n+1}, Tx_n) \\ &\leq \alpha^2 d(x_n, x_{n-1}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_{n+3}, x_{n+2}) &= d(Tx_{n+2}, Tx_{n+1}) \\ &\leq \alpha^3 d(x_n, x_{n-1}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_{n+k}, x_{n+k-1}) &= d(Tx_{n+k-1}, Tx_{n+k-2}) \\ &\leq \alpha^k d(x_n, x_{n-1}) \quad k \in N^* \end{aligned}$$

If (Z_2) holds, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(Tx, Ty) &\leq \beta[d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty)] \\
 &\leq \beta d(x, Tx) + \beta d(y, x) + \beta d(x, Tx) + \beta d(Tx, Ty) \\
 &= 2\beta d(x, Tx) + \beta d(x, y) + \beta d(Tx, Ty) \\
 d(Tx, Ty) - \beta d(Tx, Ty) &\leq 2\beta d(x, Tx) + \beta d(x, y) \\
 (1 - \beta)d(Tx, Ty) &\leq 2\beta d(x, Tx) + \beta d(x, y) \\
 d(Tx, Ty) &\leq \left(\frac{2\beta}{1 - \beta}\right)d(x, Tx) + \left(\frac{\beta}{1 - \beta}\right)d(x, y) \quad 0 \leq \beta < 0.5
 \end{aligned}$$

denoting

$$\delta = \max\left\{\alpha, \frac{\beta}{1 - \beta}, \frac{\gamma}{1 - \gamma}\right\}. \quad (1.1)$$

where δ satisfy $0 \leq \delta < 1$.

Using Z_2 for $x, y \in X$, then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(Tx, Ty) &\leq \left(\frac{2\beta}{1 - \beta}\right)d(x, Tx) + \left(\frac{\beta}{1 - \beta}\right)d(x, y) \\
 d(Tx, Ty) &\leq 2\left(\frac{\beta}{1 - \beta}\right)d(x, Tx) + \left(\frac{\beta}{1 - \beta}\right)d(x, y)
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $\delta = \frac{\beta}{1 - \beta}$,

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq 2\delta d(x, Tx) + \delta d(x, y). \quad (1.3)$$

If Z_3 holds, from theorem 1.1, suppose $0 \leq \delta < 1$ then

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(Tx, Ty) &\leq \gamma[d(x, Ty), d(y, Tx)] \\
 &\leq \gamma d(x, Ty) + [d(y, x) + d(x, Ty) + d(Ty, Tx)] \\
 (1 - \gamma)d(Tx, Ty) &\leq 2\gamma d(x, Ty) + \gamma d(y, x) \\
 d(Tx, Ty) &\leq d(x, Ty) + \frac{\gamma}{1 - \gamma}d(x, y) \quad 0 \leq \gamma < 0.5
 \end{aligned}$$

In a similar manner, Let consider,

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(Tx, Ty) &\leq \left(\frac{2\gamma}{1 - \gamma}\right)d(x, Ty) + \left(\frac{\gamma}{1 - \gamma}\right)d(x, y) \\
 d(Tx, Ty) &\leq 2\left(\frac{\gamma}{1 - \gamma}\right)d(x, Ty) + \left(\frac{\gamma}{1 - \gamma}\right)d(x, y)
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $\delta = \frac{\gamma}{1 - \gamma}$, to obtain

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq 2\delta d(x, Ty) + \delta d(x, y). \quad (1.4)$$

Remark 2: Suppose $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ is a normed linear space, then (1.3) becomes

$$\|Tx - Ty\| \leq 2\delta\|x - Tx\| + \delta\|x - y\|, \quad (1.5)$$

for all $x, y \in X$ and where $0 \leq \delta < 1$ is defined by (1.1)

Bosede used (1.5) to find the fixed point theorems for some iteration processes with generalized Zamfirescu mappings in uniformly convex Banach spaces (see [3]).

Our aim in this paper is to establish some fixed point theorems for some iteration processes with generalized Zamfirescu mappings in uniformly convex Banach spaces. The generalized Zamfirescu mapping defined in this paper is better than the one defined by Ciric (2003) and Bosede (2009) (see [4, 5]). We shall use an iterative scheme (2.3) and the contraction mapping as indicated below: Let X be a non-empty closed convex subset of a normed linear space X and $T : X \rightarrow X$ a self map of X , then

$$\|Tx - Ty\| \leq (2\delta\|x - Tx\| + \delta\|x - y\|)e^{\|x - Tx\|} \quad (1.6)$$

where $0 \leq \delta < 1$ is defined by (1.1) and e^x denotes the exponential function of $x \in X$

2 Preliminaries

Suppose Q be a closed and convex subset of a Banach space X and $T : Q \rightarrow Q$ a mapping which satisfies the condition

$$d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty) \leq ad(x, y) \quad (2.1)$$

$\forall x, y \in Q$, where $2 \leq a < 4$.

Let $x_0 \in Q$ be arbitrary and sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be a sequence defined by

$$x_{n+1} = \frac{1}{2}(x_n + Tx_n), n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (2.2)$$

Mann Iterative Scheme [6]

Let $x_0 \in Q$ be arbitrary, $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ be a sequence defined by

$$x_{n+1} = (1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_nTx_n, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (2.3)$$

satisfying conditions $0 \leq \alpha_n \leq 1$ and $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) = \infty$.

Ishikawa Iterative Scheme [7]

Let $x_0 \in Q$ be arbitrary, $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ be a sequence defined by

$$\begin{aligned} y_n &= (1 - \beta_n)x_n + \beta_nTx_n, \\ x_{n+1} &= (1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_nTy_n, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

with $\{\alpha_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ and $\{\beta_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ being sequences of real number, satisfying the following conditions $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \alpha_n = \infty$, $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \beta_n = \infty$ and $0 \leq \alpha_n, \beta_n \leq 1$.

Noor Iterative Scheme [8]

Let $x_0 \in Q$ be arbitrary, $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ be a sequence defined by

$$\begin{aligned} z_n &= (1 - \gamma_n)x_n + \gamma_nTy_n \\ y_n &= (1 - \beta_n)x_n + \beta_nTx_n, \\ x_{n+1} &= (1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_nTz_n, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

with $\{\alpha_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$, $\{\beta_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ and $\{\gamma_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ being sequences of real number, satisfying the following conditions $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \alpha_n = \infty$, $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \beta_n = \infty$, $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \gamma_n = \infty$ and $0 \leq \alpha_n, \beta_n, \gamma_n \leq 1$.

Using the contractive condition (2.1) and iteration (2.2), Ćirić in [4] established the following results:

Theorem 2.1 Let Q be a closed and convex subset of a Banach space X with the norm $\|x\| = d(x, 0)$, $x \in Q$ and a mapping $T : Q \rightarrow Q$ which satisfies the contractive definition (2.1). Let $x_0 \in Q$ be arbitrary sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ defined iteratively by (2.2). Then, T has at least one fixed point.

Remark 3: The proof of Theorem 2.1 is contained in [4]. Our aim in this paper is to establish fixed point theorems for Ishikawa (2.4) and Mann (2.3) iterative schemes respectively in uniformly convex Banach spaces for the class of Zamfirescu mappings, using the contractive definition (1.6)

Remark 4: The contractive definition (1.6) is well defined. Iterative scheme (2.4) used in our result is more general than iterative scheme (2.3) used by Bosede in [3], iterative scheme (2.2) used by Ćirić and others in literature (see [3-5, 9-29]).

Suppose $\beta_n = 0, \forall n \in N$ in the Ishikawa Iteration (2.4), we obtain iteration (2.3) which is the iteration used by Bosede, also suppose $\alpha_n = \frac{1}{2}, \forall n \in N$ in the Ishikawa iteration (2.3), we obtain iteration (2.2) used by Ćirić [4] in Theorem 2.1 above.

The following result establishes a fixed point theorem for Mann iteration process for the class of Zamfirescu mappings in uniformly convex Banach spaces.

3 Main Result

Theorem 3.1

Suppose $T : Q \rightarrow Q$ be a selfmap, Q be a closed and convex subset of a uniformly convex Banach space X , satisfying contractive condition (1.6). Let $x_0 \in Q$ be arbitrary and a sequence of $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ defined iteratively by (2.3) converges strongly to the fixed point of T .

Proof

Considering iterative scheme (2.3), contractive definition (1.6) and triangular inequalities, for any arbitrary $x_0 \in Q$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|x_{n+1} - p\| &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_nTx_n - p\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_nTx_n - \alpha_np - (1 - \alpha_n)p\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)(x_n - p) + \alpha_n(Tx_n - p)\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)(x_n - p) + \alpha_n(Tx_n - p)\| \\
 &\leq \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n\|Tx_n - p\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n\|Tx_n - Tp\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n\|Tp - Tx_n\| \\
 &\leq \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n(2\delta\|p - Tp\| + \delta\|p - x_n\|)e^{\|Tp - p\|} \\
 &\leq \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n(2\delta\|p - p\| + \delta\|x_n - p\|)e^{\|p - p\|} \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n(2\delta(0) + \delta\|x_n - p\|)e^0 \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n(0 + \delta\|x_n - p\|) \\
 &\leq \|(1 - \alpha_n + \alpha_n\delta)\|x_n - p\|
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

where $0 \leq \alpha_n < 1, 0 \leq \delta < 1$ and $0 \leq (1 - \alpha_n + \alpha_n\delta) < 1$, gives

$$\|x_{n+1} - p\| \leq \|x_n - p\| \tag{3.2}$$

This shows that $\|x_n - p\|$ is a monotone decreasing sequence. From (3.2) $\|x_n - p\| \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then, iterative scheme (2.3) converges strongly to the fixed point of T .

Hence, completes the proof.

Remark 5: The iterative scheme (2.4) used in our next result is more general than the iterative scheme (2.2) used by Ciric (1990). Suppose $\beta_n = 0 \forall n \in N$ in (2.4), we obtain an iterative scheme (2.3).

Remark 6: The contraction definition used in (1.6) is more general than (1.5) used by Bosedo (2009) in the following sense:

Suppose $e^0 = 1$ in (1.6), we obtain (1.5) $\forall x, y \in X$

The following result establish a fixed point theorem for Ishikawa iteration process for the class of Zamfirescu mappings in uniformly convex Banach spaces.

Theorem 3.2

Suppose $T : Q \rightarrow Q$ be a selfmap and Q be as in Theorem 3.1 above. Let $x_0 \in Q$ be arbitrary and a sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^\infty$ be defined by (2.4) iteratively. Hence, Ishikawa iterative scheme converges strongly to the fixed point of T.

Proof

From Theorem 1.1, it was established that T has a unique fixed point in Q, that is $p = Tp$ such that $p \in Q$. This study need to show that the sequence $\|x_n - p\|$ is monotone decreasing. Considering the iterative scheme (2.4), contractive definition (1.6) and triangular inequalities. For arbitrary $x_0 \in Q$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|x_{n+1} - p\| &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_nTy_n - p\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_nTy_n - \alpha_np - (1 - \alpha_n)p\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)(x_n - p) + \alpha_n(Ty_n - p)\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)(x_n - p) + \alpha_n(Ty_n - p)\| \\
 &\leq \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n\|Ty_n - p\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n\|Ty_n - Tp\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n\|Tp - Ty_n\| \\
 &\leq \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n(2\delta\|p - Tp\| + \delta\|p - y_n\|)e^{\|Tp - p\|} \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n(2\delta\|p - p\| + \delta\|y_n - p\|)e^{\|p - p\|} \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n(2\delta(0) + \delta\|y_n - p\|)e^0 \\
 &= \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n(0 + \delta\|y_n - p\|) \\
 &\leq \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n\delta\|y_n - p\| \tag{3.3}
 \end{aligned}$$

However, $y_n = (1 - \beta_n)x_n + \beta_nTx_n$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|y_n - p\| &\leq \|(1 - \beta_n)x_n + \beta_nTx_n - p\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \beta_n)(x_n - p) + \beta_n(Tx_n - p)\| \\
 &\leq \|(1 - \beta_n)\|x_n - p\| + \beta_n\|Tx_n - p\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \beta_n)\|x_n - p\| + \beta_n\|Tx_n - Tp\| \\
 &= \|(1 - \beta_n)\|x_n - p\| + \beta_n\|Tp - Tx_n\| \\
 &\leq \|(1 - \beta_n)\|x_n - p\| + \beta_n(2\delta\|p - Tp\| + \delta\|p - x_n\|)e^{\|Tp - p\|} \\
 &= \|(1 - \beta_n)\|x_n - p\| + \beta_n(2\delta\|p - p\| + \delta\|x_n - p\|)e^{\|p - p\|} \\
 &= \|(1 - \beta_n)\|x_n - p\| + \beta_n(2\delta(0) + \delta\|x_n - p\|)e^0 \\
 &= \|(1 - \beta_n)\|x_n - p\| + \beta_n(0 + \delta\|x_n - p\|) \\
 &= \|(1 - \beta_n + \beta_n\delta)\|x_n - p\| \tag{3.4}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $0 \leq \beta_n < 1$, $0 \leq \delta < 1$ and $0 \leq (1 - \beta_n + \beta_n\delta) < 1$, gives

$$\|y_n - p\| \leq \|x_n - p\| \tag{3.5}$$

Substituting (3.5) into (3.3) gives

$$\begin{aligned}\|x_{n+1} - p\| &\leq \|(1 - \alpha_n)\|x_n - p\| + \alpha_n\delta\|x_n - p\| \\ &= \|(1 - \alpha_n + \alpha_n\delta)\|x_n - p\|\end{aligned}$$

Also, by observing that $0 \leq \alpha_n \leq 1$, $0 \leq \delta < 1$ and since $0 \leq (1 - \alpha_n + \alpha_n\delta) < 1$, gives

$$\|x_{n+1} - p\| \leq \|x_n - p\| \tag{3.6}$$

This shows a monotone decreasing sequence such that $\|x_n - p\|$ is monotone decreasing. From (3.6) observe that $\|x_n - p\| \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then, iterative scheme (2.4) converges strongly to the fixed point of T.

This completes the proof.

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